

A Heuristic Study on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Charismatic Leadership

Ms. Kanwal Roop Kaur¹, Ms. Sonhal Mehta²,

¹Assistant Professor, Goswami Ganesh Dutta Sanatan Dharma College, Chandigarh

²Assistant Professor, Goswami Ganesh Dutta Sanatan Dharma College, Chandigarh

Corresponding author- **Ms. Kanwal Roop Kaur**

Email-Kanwalroop.ubs@gmail.com

Abstract

In these dynamic times, a leader's continued relevance is crucial to the organisation. For the team to function at its highest level of production, the leader must be active. It's important to be adaptable to changes in the always changing environment. A leader has a great importance in creating an organisational culture that is beneficial to its employees. To comprehend conditions and responses, a leader must put himself in his followers' position. Leaders can only be effective if they are aware about the behaviour as well as the emotions of their followers. Thereby a leader's success is determined by how well they connect and collaborate with their followers. This research is an endeavour to highlight the association between Emotional Intelligence and Charismatic Leadership. By investigating the existing literature available on the association between the two some conclusions were drawn. In depth analysis was done covering 20 studies both theoretical and empirical and different countries. The results indicate that EI and its elements predict charisma in leaders and there exists a positive and significant relationship between the two. The exhaustive findings would be helpful in Human Resource and Leadership studies.

Keywords – Emotional Intelligence, Charismatic Leadership, Leadership, Leadership Review

Method

The study followed Torraco's guide and Integrative Literature Review. Firstly, articles were scanned (including their titles and abstracts), then in depth analysis of the selected articles was performed. For this purpose, multiple databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, ScienceDirect, Springer, Jstor were identified. The keyword combination used was "emotional intelligence" and "charismatic leadership", relationship between "emotional intelligence" and "charismatic leadership". The search was made within the article title, abstract and keywords. No restrictions were placed while searching the databases. The studies were critically examined by looking into the following parameters (i) focussed on relationship between EI and CL (ii) had a research methodology.

Emotional Intelligence (EI)

Emotions are feelings (such as love, happiness, fear, motivation, etc.) that arise in response to a certain situation or event. EI is just the ability to command over one's own emotions as well as the emotions of a group in a constructive manner. "EI reflects the extent to which an individual attends to, processes, and acts upon information of an emotion nature intra-personally and inter-personally" (Salovey and Mayer, 1990). Emotional intelligence (EI) "means the mental processes involved within the recognition, use, understanding, and management of one's own and others' emotional states to solve problems and regulate behaviour" (Mayer & Salovey, 1997). Emotional intelligence has often been related to better

psychological well-being which are important life outcomes (Schutte, Malouff, Thorsteinsson, Bhullar, & Rooke, 2007), high-quality social relationships (Lopes et al., 2004), and increased career success.

According to Goleman (1995), social and personal skills are the two main components of the Emotional Intelligence Model. Self-motivation, self-management, and self-awareness are the elements of personal skills whereas social communication and empathy are the part of social skills. Goleman (1995) suggests that "emotional intelligence can be improved and increased through proper training and education".

Charismatic Leadership (CL)

The use of charm, interpersonal connections, and persuasiveness to inspire the followers is defined as Charismatic Leadership. Charismatic leaders have the power to inspire and drive their employees to achieve bigger things. They aim to connect with their team members' emotions and inspire a sense of enthusiasm, trust, and purpose amongst them. This type of leadership style focuses on interpersonal interaction and engagement with the followers as compared to laissez-faire or autocratic leadership style. Such a leader has positive control over their followers' credentials, talents, intelligence, decision-making abilities, emotional stability, motivation, communication, and even all other parts of their abilities. To instil a sense of trust and dependence in their followers, charismatic leaders must communicate with optimism and fervour (Bono & Ilies, 2006).

Charismatic leaders have a keen eye for internal organisational change, keep an eye on their followers' emotions, and devise plans to keep people motivated to work toward predetermined goals.

According to earlier studies, charismatic leadership can be characterised by specific actions that take place in three separate stages. A charismatic leader recognises the demands of the followers and hears them express their displeasure with the situation at the initial phase of evaluating the environment. In the second phase, charismatic leaders create a vision and successfully convey it to their followers. The third stage, where the vision is put into action, calls on leaders to act in a dangerous and unusual way to win the support of their subordinates. Examples include willingly putting themselves in circumstances with unclear results and taking risks. (Conger & Kanungo, 1994), (Ehrhart & Klein, 2001)

Relationship between EI and CL

Palmer, Walls, Burgess, and Stough(2001) researched whether emotional intelligence correlates with transformational leadership and how it is a crucial component of effective leadership. The results depict that emotionally intelligent leaders have inspirational motivation and charisma which they utilize to inspire their followers. For exploring the hypothesis, modified version of TMMS and multifactor leadership questionnaire was employed. Although the hypothesis was not fully supported still the the relationship between the elements of transformational leadership and EI could be seen. Idealized influence sub- scales(charisma) correlated significantly with emotional monitoring scale ($r = 0.44, p < 0.01$). the relationship between emotion monitoring, management and individualized consideration could also be observed ($r = 0.55, p < 0.01, r = 0.35, p < 0.05$). But a moderate correlation exists between Inspirational motivation and Emotional monitoring ($r = 0.42, p < 0.01$), between Inspirational motivation and Emotional management ($r = 0.37, p < 0.05$). According to the authors, the leaders who pay special heed to the needs of subordinates are emotionally intelligent and can trigger transformations in the organizations.

Using a cross-sectional and descriptive design, Yildirim, N. et al. (2021) investigated the association between nursing students' leadership orientation and emotional intelligence levels. Between May and June 2019, the study involved 320 nursing students from a university in Turkey. Data were gathered through a questionnaire. The results of the Leadership Orientations Survey and the results of the overall Emotional Intelligence Evaluation Scale and its subscales showed a positive and statistically significant association ($p 0.01$). The

findings depicted that all the subscales were positively impacted by the EIES scores.

Table 1

Name of the subscale	Score	p values
People-oriented	0.889	0.05
Structure- oriented	0.531	0.05
Transformational leadership	0.426	0.05
Charismatic leadership	0.506	0.05

People-oriented leadership subscale (70.0percent), followed by structure-oriented leadership (28.2percent), charismatic leadership (25.6percent), and transformational leadership (18.2percent) subscales, was the leadership characteristic that the Emotional Intelligence Evaluation Scale score described the most. Based on these results, it was concluded that raising student nurses' emotional intelligence levels will help them acquire leadership qualities. By integrating the existing studies on the emergence of charismatic leadership behavior, Walter, F. & Bruch, H. (2009) advance a more comprehensive viewpoint. According to the study, Emotional Intelligence has been seen to have a more nuanced impact, because the leaders who are emotionally intelligent may be able to effectively combat negative affective outcomes and indulge in impression management tactics even when they are not well. It was found that managers with high EI have an easier time maintaining positive work attitudes, mostly independent of their emotional states, and therefore suggests that EI should consequently weaken the link between leaders' positive affect and attitudes.

Elbers, N. et al. (2007) looked into the effectiveness of charismatic leaders in communicating organisational principles to their followers as well as the contribution of emotional intelligence to the promotion of organisational values by charismatic leaders. Multiple regression was used to examine the data, which was acquired from some subordinates and leaders in a Dutch retail organisation. It was anticipated that charismatic, emotionally intelligent leaders would oversee teams in which there is a better connection between the leaders' personal values and the team members' perceptions of the organization's core principles. Only a few value orientations were found to support these hypotheses. For innovative and people-oriented leaders, the expected mediating role of EI in the association between charismatic leadership was validated along with the suitability between the leaders' personal values and how employees view the organization's common values. The findings also suggested that leader judgments of their own performance can be just as important as employee

ratings. Although followers may not find their leader to be charismatic, if a leader believes they are charismatic, it affects how their teams view values. Only the leaders' self-ratings of their charismatic leadership were shown to be connected with EI. According to the study, there is no clear correlation between EI, charismatic leadership, and organisational culture because there are other factors that may have a bigger impact on how individuals perceive organisational culture than just leadership style. Depending on the department and the company, different leaders may contribute differently to the corporate culture.

A paradigm for methodically analysing how specific emotions may affect charismatic and transformative leadership was proposed by Connelly et al. (2013) after reviewing the body of theoretical and empirical literature on the topic. In order to have a better knowledge of how emotions impact leader communication, motivation, interpersonal interactions, and relationship management with followers, it examined the emotion framework. The study's findings showed that various leadership styles are likely to exhibit various emotional patterns, both consciously and unconsciously, that are congruent with their frames of reference for engaging with and leading followers. Additionally, followers of leaders who employ various leadership philosophies are likely to exhibit a variety of emotional inclinations. It asserts that distinct emotions are displayed at various stages of the leadership process, from the first point when a vision is formed and conveyed through the point when vision-related goals have been accomplished, amended, or abandoned. Nassif, A. et al. (2020) employed a two-sample inquiry to contrast the relationships between some of the leadership philosophies—ethical leadership, virtuous leadership, and socialised charismatic leadership—and a number of follower-leader outcomes (sample drawn from UK, US and Canada industries). To determine the degree of view the replication in the findings, the study of sample 2 of subordinates was conducted. According to the research, the Brown et al. (2005) Ethical Leadership Scale was the sole significant, singular predictor of perceived leader effectiveness, leader in-role performance, and follower ethicality. Furthermore, it was claimed that ethical and virtuous leadership both contributed to the distinctive variation in followers' performance outside of their assigned roles. The leadership attribute from Sample 1 and the TL elements from Sample 2 cannot be disregarded while keeping employees well-being in mind. Furthermore, it asserts that most leaders appear to be unable or reluctant to employ many strategies. According to

the article, leaders often have a wide range of behavioural options that should be researched in order to get the greatest results possible for the study's outcomes. Using the behavioural Emotional Intelligence model, Haricharan, S. J. (2022) investigated the connections between executive managers' leadership performance and their emotional intelligence abilities. This was done in the South African public sector. 35 executive managers who were evaluated by 230 respondents on Emotional and Social Competence Inventory (ESCI) had their emotional intelligence skills tested. Leadership performance was evaluated using nominations from many sources from 371 respondents. Rank correlation coefficients from Spearman and an analysis of variance were used to assess the hypotheses. According to the findings, there is a strong positive link between leadership ability and each of the four EI competency clusters, namely self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, and relationship management. The most significant relationships were seen between emotional self-awareness, flexibility, inspirational leadership, and emotional intelligence skills. The competency gap between the managers and their performance showed a strong negative link. Consequently, this quantitative study substantiated the favourable association between EI and leadership performance in the South African public sector using the behavioural technique.

Yang, Z., and Zhu, J. (2016) developed a hypothesis model to examine the mechanism underlying the influence of charismatic leadership behaviour on leadership effectiveness. They included employee psychological empowerment and emotional intelligence in their model. Between October 2015 and March 2016, a study of 207 private businesses in Beijing, Tianjin, and Shandong was carried out. Using descriptive analysis, correlation, and variable path analysis in structural equation modelling, the data was examined in SPSS 17 software. The findings demonstrate that the more pronounced the charismatic leadership behaviour, the higher will be the improvement in leaders' effectiveness, which depends on the encouragement of organizational cohesion and the perception of employees as having a lead character as well as other psychological factors that promote empowerment. According to the study, high emotionally intelligent subordinates are better able to enhance organizational citizenship based on task requirements, whereas low emotionally intelligent subordinates are better able to enhance employees' job satisfaction and performance through charismatic leadership behaviour.

Chunxu, Y. & Yanlin, L. (2011) taking the viewpoint of charismatic leadership and followers' emotional intelligence, analyzed the link between the factors in the organizational identification process utilizing a plethora of literature. According to this study, charismatic leaders significantly influenced their subordinates' organizational identification. Charismatic leadership can enhance members' cognitive abilities and encourage the internalization of organizational ideals in order to foster an environment for the organization that inspires a sense of belongingness among its members. The emotional intelligence of subordinates was found to be positively influenced by charismatic leaders, who in turn had an impact on their own organizational identity. According to the research, the association between charismatic leadership and followers' organizational affiliation is modulated and successfully modified by followers' emotional intelligence.

When people characterise those they believe to be charismatic leaders, Parry et al. (2019) looked at whether followers feel any sense of belonging. The participants in the study wrote a metaphor for their charismatic leader and named a film or genre that best depicted the traits of their leader. The replies were analysed using a mixed-methods aesthetic narrative methodology. A qualitative analysis was developed for the investigation. Five different groups of managers from middle level who were enrolled in organisational behaviour and leadership courses in the UK, Melbourne, and Australia provided the data for the study in two waves using the questionnaire approach. The study found that one of the most crucial factors in a leader's success i.e. a better leader - follower relationship is when a leader has a good level of relationship with the community.

By taking into account humility's effect on the behaviours and efficacy of this kind of leadership, Nielsen et al. (2009) enhanced the idea of humility's function in socialised charismatic leadership. The impacts of humility on the manifestation and efficacy of three crucial socialised charismatic leader behaviors—vision production, vision implementation, and communication—were examined. Humility is an undervalued but crucial component of socialised charismatic leadership. According to the study, humility is a desirable quality that prevents leaders from becoming overly self-absorbed, enables them to understand themselves and gain perspective in their interactions with followers, and that attributed humility helps to maximise the outcomes that can be expected from followers. It claims that humility enables a leader to comprehend followers' ideals, seek out others'

viewpoints, and see oneself in relation to others. It aids in creating an inspiring vision. The vision is then put into life by humility through effective collaboration with followers and by connecting followers' self-concepts to the vision.

Walter and Bruch (2007) conducted their study on the importance of EI and positive mood for predicting charismatic leadership behaviour. For data collection 34 leaders and 165 followers were questioned using Job related affective well-being scale, Wong and Law's (2002) scale and MLQ 5x-short Leadership questionnaire. The hypotheses framed for this study was accepted as the results concluded that individuals who have a better and a positive mood think divergently, solve problems quickly, create exigent vision statements, evoke emotions among their followers which will ultimately lead to charismatic behaviours. It is also observed that social interactions of leaders with followers is an important component for validation of EI and CL. They reported that leaders' positive mood and leaders' charismatic leadership behaviour are positively and significantly correlated ($r = 0.43$, $p < 0.05$); the relationship between CL and EI ($r = 0.54$, $p < 0.05$) is also positive and significant. It was also discovered that a low EI leader will show charisma as long as he is in a positive mood and a leader high on emotional intelligence shows charismatic behaviours even in a bad mood. The results of factor analysis and hierarchical regression analysis further supported the study.

Using the Conger and Kanungo model (1994) and Riggio's Social skills Inventory (1989) to assess the association between social, emotional skills and charismatic leadership, Groves (2005) collected data from 108 leaders and 325 followers. They empirically justified the relationship between emotional skills and charismatic leadership ($r = 0.71$, $p < 0.01$) which is a very high correlation. An integration between leader skills, followers' attitudes and contextual variables was also examined. The correlation between CL and social control ($r = 0.27$, $p < 0.01$); between CL and emotional expressivity ($r = 0.24$, $p < 0.05$) whereas CL not related to control of emotions ($r = 0.11$, n.s.). Additionally, the relationship between organizational change magnitude and CL ($r = 0.40$, $p < 0.01$) but emotional expression and social control were related to organizations' magnitude of change. Self presentation and social role playing abilities of leaders induce charisma which is utilized to motivate the followers for organization change time period. Emotional skills are required to perceive the charisma in leaders so that they can understand the needs of their followers.

He also did another study in 2005 mapping gender differences in CL and emotional and social skills. He mapped the gender social/emotional competencies using the same instruments and came to the conclusion that female leaders are more charismatic as compared to male leaders. They consistently display higher emotional and social skills and they are more empathetic to their followers and are better at expressing their emotions. As per the observation of the author the ability to detect and control one's expression is related to charismatic behaviour. Earlier studies confirm that women are better communicators than their male counterparts in the case of non-verbal channels. Also, the facial decoding skills are found more in women than men.

With the help of C-K Leadership Inventory and Social Intelligence questionnaire, Duggal and Agrawal (2013) researched on the role of Social and Emotional Intelligence in formation of Charismatic leadership behaviour. The authors gathered the data from 94 employees of different companies and discovered that there exists a positive and significant relationship between the EI and CL ($r = 0.728, p < 0.05$) whereas weak relationship between EI and SI ($r = 0.475, p < 0.05$). A leader will be considered as a Charismatic leader when he exhibits strong emotional association with his followers and lead them in an extraordinary way. The researchers also conducted regression analysis in this respect which also supported correlation results. They could gather that regression coefficient value between EI and CL is 0.658 which depicts that 65.8 percent transition in CL is due to EI. According to them, there is a need to lead the followers in an influential way rather than traditional. It calls for skillful and influential leadership skills. The productivity of the organization also depends upon how well the people in the organizations bond with each other and understand each other's emotions. A leader who is emotionally conscious inculcates clear values among their subordinates. Emotional intelligence highly impacts the charismatic leadership behaviour.

In looking at the correlation between EI and CL, Tareq and Khazaei(2017) collected data from MBA students using Questionnaire for Charismatic Leadership in Organizations, Emotional Intelligence Appraisal measure. Authors followed Goleman's model which bifurcates EI into four dimensions namely (a) self-awareness (b) self-management (c) social awareness (d) relationship management and then analysing their relationship with charismatic leadership. 70 percent of the variance in CL is demonstrated by empathy, self-awareness, self-management and social skills. The organizations should focus their energy on developing emotional

traits in the managers for competitive advantage. Contamination of emotions can be done only by the leaders who can oversee emotions in self and others. Such contamination will ultimately lead to Charismatic leadership behaviour. For achievement of goals also charisma is required as it will help in inspiring the employees. Leaders are expected to step into the shoes of their followers to better understand their emotions and empathize with their subordinates when they are facing troubles in their lives. They also mentioned about Martin Luther King Jr. that he displayed sympathy towards his followers' emotions which made him a great leader. Banks, Engemann, Williams, Gooty, McCauley, Medaugh(2016) conducted a meta-analysis on CL taking predictors such as Leader Personality, Leader Intelligence and Leader Demographic Characteristics, dimensions of CL such as Idealized influence(attribution and behaviour), Inspirational motivation/vision and objective outcomes such as Task performance, OCB, Group or firm performance. This research is in line with the previous work done in the domain of CL. According to the authors, there is moderate to strong association between general intelligence and CL. Higher the cognitive abilities higher are the prospects of leaders to analyse complex situations and provide solutions that are exotic. CL creates creativity, better sense, better emotional tone amongst the leaders. They agree that cognitive abilities(general intelligence) is positively associated with CL. As per their recommendations, more theories need to be developed in the domain of emotions linked with leadership as they found majority of the studies which conceptualized emotional intelligence not an ability but a skill. For predicting CL there is a need for digging deeper and building more theories which justify the relationship between the two. They also observed that despite the plethora of studies verifying that women display more charisma than men, women are not perceived to be charismatic in leadership roles.

In looking at the correlation between EI and CL, Biswas and Rahman(2021) took the help of MLQ 5X and EQI questionnaire and sample size of 356 respondents. Pearson correlation and regression was performed for the study which revealed that all the elements of EI are positively and significantly related to CL namely self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills ($r = 0.64, p < 0.001$; $r = 0.62, p < 0.001$; $r = 0.65, p < 0.001$; $r = 0.63, p < 0.001$; $r = 0.59, p < 0.001$ respectively). The regression results also supported the hypotheses and helped in proving that all the elements of EI certainly have a strong impact on the CL. They highlighted and pointed that efforts should be made

by the firms to uplift their members' social skills for efficiency at administrative levels. Charisma which is an essential part of transformation comes out to be the strongest predictor.

Pessimistic relationship between EI and CL

Antonakis (2003) gave valuable comments on the article written by Prati, Douglas, Ferris, Ammeter, and Buckley (2003) and examined whether EI is crucial for CL behaviour or not. He mentioned about some studies which show that EI is not related to CL and it is not an important predictor of CL, while some studies show there exists a relationship. He mentioned that Charisma needs vision and moral conviction not EI. According to his notion, there is not sufficient evidence to justify that large portion of leadership effectiveness is explained by EI. He told that emotional outbursts like anger of the team leader also affects his team members negatively.

Aziz and Hamdi (2019) examined whether emotional intelligence has some significant association with CL or not. Using Conger et al. (1997) and Brackett et al. (2006) questionnaires for CL and EI respectively they could gather that EI is not a unique predictor of CL. Based on the analysis of data, they found out that social management and managing of emotions share a significant relationship with charisma ($\beta = 0.544$, p value= 0.14); ($\beta = 0.506$, p - value = 0.024 respectively) whereas use, understanding and perceiving emotions share not a significant one ($\beta = 0.209$, p -value = 0.262); ($\beta = -0.064$, p -value= 0.695); ($\beta = -0.301$, p -value= 0.184 respectively). As per the authors, a leader who is well aware about his own emotions, as well as the emotions of others, display an increased level of charisma. Social management skill also plays a major role in predicting charismatic behaviour in the leadership style. The negative relationship of the independent variables with charisma was because of the local culture that managers don't directly question their employees on the issues that they might be facing in the organization. As a result their subordinates feel that their leader is not sympathetic and empathetic towards them. They also reported that in order to increase the performance of the employees and to attain the goals, non-financial methods such as charisma can be used. A leader is expected to put himself in the shoes of others for a better understanding of the emotions of his followers.

Conclusion

The purpose of this review was to view the changes and trends within the past years and see how charismatic leadership and emotional intelligence and the relationship between the two has developed. Researches over the time have also

devised considering emotional intelligence as a possible foundation of charismatic leadership. With the evolving changes in the field of Human Resource Management, these terms have evolved newer bonds. The studies reveal that leaders with high emotional intelligence engage more in activities relating to leadership and trigger changes in the organisation which make sense. Such charismatic leaders combat negative outcomes and maintain a good impression in the organisation to cope up with the followers. Also, the leaders judgement of his own acts helps the followers to take the correct and thoughtful action in time of need. The results also suggest that in order to create an atmosphere for the organisation that fosters a feelings of belonging among its members, charismatic leadership can improve members' cognitive skills and support the internalisation of organisational ideals. The results also vary in the review because of the variety of emotions that are displayed by individuals in same situations as well. The variety of such different emotions and the change in emotions over time act as a limitation to the discovery of clear relationship between the two. Moreover, it's not just emotional intelligence that influences the charismatic leadership traits in the individual, but there are other factors also that contribute. The paper would hence contribute to the field of HRM.

References

1. Almeida Santos, J., Sanches Amorim, M. C., & Hoyos Guevara, A. J. de. (2018). Urban Sprawl and Consequences of Poorly Managed Expansion: the Case of São Paulo in Brazil. In *Journal on Innovation and Sustainability. RISUS ISSN 2179-3565* (Vol. 9, Issue 2). <https://doi.org/10.24212/2179-3565.2018v9i2p55-66>
2. Antonakis, J. (2003). Why "Emotional Intelligence" Does Not Predict Leadership Effectiveness: a Comment on Prati, Douglas, Ferris, Ammeter, and Buckley (2003). *The International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 11(4), 355–361. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb028980>
3. Ashkanasy, N.M., Härtel, C.E.J., Daus, C.S. (2002) Diversity and emotion: the new frontiers in organizational behavior research. *Journal of Management*, 28(3), 307-338.
4. Aziz, M. F. (2019). *Does Emotional Intelligence Predict Charisma in the Leaders? VII*(7), 244–255.
5. Banks, G. C., Engemann, K. N., Williams, C. E., Gooty, J., McCauley, K. D., & Medaugh, M. R. (2017). A meta-analytic review and future research agenda of charismatic leadership.

- Leadership Quarterly*, 28(4), 508–529.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.leaqua.2016.12.003>
6. Barling, J., Slater F., Kelloway, E.K.(2000). Transformational leadership and emotional intelligence: an exploratory study. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*. 21 (3), 157 – 161
 7. Biswas, M., & Ferdausy, S. (2015). *Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Styles at the Private Commercial Banks of Bangladesh Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Leadership Styles at the Private Commercial Banks of Bangladesh*. 30(February 2020), 249–272.
 8. Biswas, M., & Rahman, M. S. (2021). Do the Elements of Emotional Intelligence Determine Charismatic Leadership? *Business Perspective Review*, 3(1), 24–40.
<https://doi.org/10.38157/business-perspective-review.v3i1.256>
 9. Bono, J. E., & Ilies, R. (2006). Charisma, positive emotions and mood contagion. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 17(4), 317–334
 10. Connelly, S., Gaddis, B., & Helton-Fauth, W. (2013). A Closer Look at the Role of Emotions in Transformational and Charismatic Leadership. *Transformational and Charismatic Leadership: The Road Ahead 10th Anniversary Edition*, 299–327.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/s1479-357120130000005023>
 11. De Hoogh, A.H.B., Den Hartog, D.N., Koopman, P.L., Thierry, H. Van den Berg, P.T, Van der Weide, J.G., Wilderom, C.P.M. (2005). Leader motives, charismatic leadership, and subordinates' work attitude in the profit and voluntary sector. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 16, 17–38.
 12. Duggal, T., & Agrawal, A. (2013). Impact of Social and Emotional Intelligence on Charismatic Leadership. *FIIB Business Review*, 2(3), 82–89.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/2455265820130311>
 13. Elbers, N., Ascalon, E., & Gorgievski, M.J. (2007). Charismatic leadership, emotional intelligence and values in organizations.
 14. Groves, K. S. (2005). Gender Differences in Social and Emotional Skills and Charismatic Leadership. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 11(3), 30–46.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/107179190501100303>
 15. Groves, K. S. (2005). Linking leader skills, follower attitudes, and contextual variables via an integrated model of Charismatic leadership. *Journal of Management*, 31(2), 255–277.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206304271765>
 16. Haricharan, S. J. (2022). Is the leadership performance of public service executive managers related to their emotional intelligence? *SA Journal of Human Resource Management*, 20.
<https://doi.org/10.4102/sajhrm.v20i0.1773>
 17. Higgs, M., & Aitken, P. (2003). An exploration of the relationship between emotional intelligence and leadership potential. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18(7–8), 814–823.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/02683940310511890>
 18. Nassif, A. G., Hackett, R. D., & Wang, G. (2020). Ethical, Virtuous, and Charismatic Leadership: An Examination of Differential Relationships with Follower and Leader Outcomes. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 172(3), 581–603. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-020-04491-8>
 19. Nielsen, R., Marrone, J. A., & Slay, H. S. (2009). A New Look at Humility: Exploring the Humility Concept and Its Role in Socialized Charismatic Leadership. *Journal of Leadership & Organizational Studies*, 17(1), 33–43.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1548051809350892>
 20. Noureen, S., Ahmad, N., & Chaudhry, M. (2020). Emotional Intelligence and Charismatic Leadership Relation With the Moderating Effect of Leader-Member Exchange: Empirical Analysis From Qatar. *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, 17(7), 12843–12856.
<https://archives.palarch.nl/index.php/jae/article/view/4969>
 21. Palmer, B., Walls, M., Burgess, Z., & Stough, C. (2001). Emotional intelligence and effective leadership. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22(1), 5–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730110380174>
 22. Parry, K., Cohen, M., Bhattacharya, S., North-Samardzic, A., & Edwards, G. (2019). Charismatic leadership: Beyond love and hate and toward a sense of belonging? *Journal of Management & Organization*, 25(03), 398–413.
<https://doi.org/10.1017/jmo.2019.28>
 23. Rosete, D., & Ciarrochi, J. (2005). Emotional intelligence and its relationship to workplace performance outcomes of leadership effectiveness. *Leadership and Organization Development Journal*, 26(5), 388–399.
<https://doi.org/10.1108/01437730510607871>
 24. Tareq, M., Khazaei, H., Khazaei, A. (2017, September 27-29). *Emotional Intelligence and Charismatic Leadership* [Paper presentation]. 14th International Conference on Innovation and Management, Wuhan, China.

25. Walter, F., & Bruch, H. (2009). An affective events model of charismatic leadership behavior: A review, theoretical integration, and research agenda. *Journal of Management*, 35(6), 1428–1452.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206309342468>
26. Walter, F., & Bruch, H. (2009). An Affective Events Model of Charismatic Leadership Behavior: A Review, Theoretical Integration, and Research Agenda. *Journal of Management*, 35(6), 1428–1452.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0149206309342468>
27. Yang, Z., & Zhu, J. (2016). Charismatic leadership behavior and leadership effectiveness: the moderating role of subordinates' emotional intelligence and the mediating role of psychological empowerment. *Revista de Cercetare Si Interventie Sociala*, 55, 158–184.
28. Yao Chunxu, & Liu Yanlin. (2011). Notice of Retraction: Charismatic leadership and organizational identification: The mediating role of followers' emotional intelligence. *2011 International Conference on Business Management and Electronic Information*.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/icbmei.2011.5920477>
29. Yildirim, N., Kantek, F., & Yilmaz, F. A. (2021). Relationships between leadership orientations and emotional intelligence in nursing students. *Perspectives in Psychiatric Care*, 58(3), 903–909.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/ppc.12871>